

1 **CCL7 is a marker of coronary disease activity in humans with high CRP.**

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6 C-reactive protein is an acute phase protein of the innate immune system, produced by the liver and
7 released into the circulation early in the immune response to a variety of sterile and non-sterile triggers,
8 during inflammatory stress. High blood CRP is a known indicator or predictor of cardiovascular disease
9 risk. It is not completely understood why high CRP denotes risk of cardiovascular disease. We measured
10 total transcription in the blood of humans with very low CRP (less than 0.25) or high CRP (greater than 60)
11 to identify factors that explain elevated risk of heart disease associated with expression of an inflammatory
12 marker. We identified high expression of the chemokine ligand CCL7 in the blood of humans with CRP.
13 We recently described activation of CCL7 in the basic cellular subunit of the atherosclerotic plaque, the
14 foam cell, in response to oxidized LDL, and in the atherosclerotic plaque itself. Together the data provide
15 strong evidence indicating a causative or contributory role for CCL7 in progression to heart disease in
16 humans.
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